

Additional file 5: Scatterplot of the log₂ relative expression values of 1462 transcription factor genes between cold acclimated and deacclimated and between cold acclimated and non-acclimated plants of *Arabidopsis thaliana*. The expression values were determined using qRT-PCR (TF platform) or the Affymetrix Genechip *Arabidopsis* Gene 1.0 ST Array (Microarray).